

Federation of Finnish Learned Societies – CoARA Action Plan

Background, strategy and change approach

The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV) is one of the first signatories of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA). As an active member of the CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment), TSV contributes to several Working Groups (WGs) and coordinates the National Chapter Finland. As outlined in this 4-year CoARA Action Plan, TSV is committed to advancing responsible research and assessment practices in Finland and internationally. The board of the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies approved the CoARA Action Plan on 2 September 2024.

Advancing responsible research and assessment practices is one of the four priorities in [TSV Strategy for years 2024–2030](#):

- We reform the evaluation culture in cooperation with the entire scientific and research community
- We create assessment practices that value ethics, openness, diversity, societal impact, and well-being at work
- We want the volunteer work and activities of researchers for the benefit of the research community and society to be rewarded
- We develop research community-based assessment of publication channels, scientific quality and societal impact

About the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies

The [Federation of Finnish Learned Societies](#) (TSV), established in 1899, is a national co-operative body for learned societies in Finland. A public non-profit organisation funded by the Ministry of Education and Culture, it has a membership of 294 learned societies and four academies from all fields of arts and sciences.

TSV contributes to the co-operation between learned societies, supports and develops scholarly communication and publishing, and promotes awareness and usage of research results. It also supports its member societies in science policy discussion. TSV hosts two independent expert bodies instituted by the ministry: the [Committee for Public Information](#) (TJNK) and the [Finnish National Board on Research Integrity](#) (TENK).

By signing ARRA, TSV reinforced its role as an advocate for responsible evaluation. TSV is also a signatory of the **DORA Declaration** (2020) and the **Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information** (2024). TSV is committed to supporting the entire Finnish research community in its journey towards a quality focused assessment culture that recognises the full diversity and impact of researchers' work. This encompasses universities, universities of applied sciences, state

research institutes, public funders and private foundations for basic, applied and practice-oriented research.

TSV is not research performing or funding organisation. Nevertheless, TSV and some of its associated expert bodies allocate grants, subsidies and prizes to organisations and individuals for scholarly publishing, organizing conferences and producing public information. TSV coordinates four national level activities related to responsible assessment in Finland:

- [Publication Forum \(since 2010\)](#): classification of publication channels by 23 field-specific expert-panels for institutional funding-allocation recognizing the diversity of outputs and languages
- [Responsible Researcher Assessment \(since 2018\)](#): development and implementation of the national recommendation on [Good Practice in Researcher Evaluation](#), including tools and training
- [National Open Science and Research Coordination \(since 2019\)](#): development of policies and architecture for open science and Open Science Monitor for institutions, including responsible assessment
- [National CoARA Chapter Finland \(since 2023\)](#): community of CoARA members, signatories and interested stakeholders for promotion and implementation of CoARA principles and commitments

In addition to CoARA, TSV actively contributes to the international collaborations to promote responsible assessment:

- [ENRESSH \(since 2014\)](#): COST-Action and community of European network for developing research assessment in the social sciences and the humanities
- [Helsinki Initiative \(since 2019\)](#): advocating recognition of multilingualism and language diversity in research assessment and funding systems
- [GraspOS \(since 2023\)](#): EU-funded project developing infrastructure, tools, guidelines and practices for open science -aware assessments
- [CoARA Working Groups \(since 2023\)](#): coordination of the WG on Multilingualism, and participation in several thematic Working Groups

TSV actions regarding CoARA commitments 2024–2027

CoARA Commitment	TSV Actions
1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research	<p>TSV coordinates the steering group for implementation of the Recommendation for the responsible evaluation of a researcher in Finland published in 2020. Implementation is supported by development of the FIN-CAM (Finnish Career-Assessment Matrix) and Narrative CV template, which enable recognition of broad range of outputs, activities and impacts of researchers.</p> <p>For the institutional level, TSV coordinates several activities supporting the recognition of diversity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Publication Forum supports recognition of diversity of outputs and languages in the funding allocation of Finnish universities• Open Science monitor and self-evaluation tool for Open Science services tracks institutional capacity for recognition of diversity• TSV has an ongoing project for developing recommendations and framework of societal impact assessment for institutions
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators	<p>TSV implements the Leiden manifesto principle “Quantitative evaluation should support qualitative, expert assessment” in evaluation of journals, conferences and book publishers. Publication Forum prioritizes expert-assessment, which can be informed with quantitative and qualitative indicators. The community-based classification is developed from the perspective of the Finnish research community, recognizes the diversity of this community’s local and international publications channels, and is produced with participation of Finnish researchers. Journal Impact Factor (JIF) is not provided to experts as indicators to support the journal evaluation.</p> <p>TSV will also investigate if the structure and operating model of the Publication Forum’s national field-specific expert panels, nominated for 4-year terms based on suggestions by the learned societies and research organisations, could be developed as a federated service for other assessment purposes, such as societal impact.</p>

CoARA Commitment	TSV Actions
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index	<p>In line with the DORA Declaration general recommendation, User Guide for Publication Forum Classification published since 2012 emphasizes that the classification is inappropriate for evaluation and comparison of individual researchers or their outputs and should in no circumstances replace expert-judgment in evaluation of individuals. According to long-term development plan for the Publication Forum Classification, the User Guide is going to be updated 2024 considering the CoARA commitments.</p> <p>TSV contributes to the Finnish national guide to publication metrics, which is a broad collaborative effort coordinated by the Finn-ARMA's publication metrics network. The responsible use of publication metrics plays a central role in the content of the guide.</p>
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment	<p>TSV will facilitate discussion within the CoARA National Chapter Finland and beyond about the Recommendation paper Ranking the university: On the effects of rankings on the academic community and how to overcome them produced by an expert group for the Universities of the Netherlands. The aim is to assess to what extent the recommendations could be taken up and implemented by the Finnish research and funding organisations.</p>
5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to	<p>TSV has personnel dedicated for the coordination and development of the responsible assessment related activities. TSV also supports internal collaboration between units and development of assessment related expertise across teams, for example by means of participation in various CoARA WGs and national networks dedicated to responsible assessment.</p>

CoARA Commitment	TSV Actions
<p>6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes</p>	<p>TSV is also committed to reviewing its criteria and processes, and those of expert bodies, for allocating grants, subsidies and prizes to organisations and individuals, and for monitoring open science, from the perspective of CoARA. Also, the long-term development plan for Publication Forum includes review of the quality classification with view to possible revision of the criteria and structure of the classification.</p> <p>TSV will develop the JUFO-portal, which is a register of over 30,000 publication channels evaluated in the Publication Forum or used for professional and science communication, as a more versatile information source about the quality, impact and openness of publication channels. This is a systematic effort to help researchers avoid predatory publishing practices and to find and utilize reliable opportunities for open access publishing.</p> <p>TSV coordinates the development of the FIN-CAM (Finnish Career-Assessment Matrix), as well as the template and guidance for Narrative CV, to support responsible and quality focused researcher assessment practices at the national level.</p> <p>TSV also collaborates internationally on development of assessment criteria, practices and tools through GraspOS EU project and thematic CoARA Working Groups (WG). TSV coordinates the WG on Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment. It also participates in the following CoARA Working Groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Reforming Academic Career Assessment• Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment• Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review• Early-and-mid-Career Researchers – Assessment and Research Culture• Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-based research, and Impacts• Evaluating Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research globally• Ethics and Research Integrity Policy in Responsible research Assessment for Data and Artificial Intelligence• Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research• Responsible metrics and indicators

CoARA Commitment	TSV Actions
7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use	TSV contributes to raising awareness about the assessment reform by <ul style="list-style-type: none">organizing national Responsible Assessment Dayorganizing webinars and seminars to inform and engage researchers, evaluators and leaders in the reform of research assessment and to advocate and monitor the change in assessment culturepublishing web pages, reports and blog posts to communicate the diverse benefits of the reform, the progress made at the national level as well as international developments on Responsible Researcher Assessment website and in co-operation with international networks (e.g., DORA Case study)Planning training on responsible assessment to researchers, assessment panels, committees, juries and other parties involved in the assessment of research, including especially Human Resources personnel
8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition	TSV coordinates the National Chapter Finland and communicates regularly on progress by means of news pieces, briefs, and reports. TSV actively seeks to engage organisations that are not CoARA signatories or members in the National Chapter. TSV facilitates the efficient collaboration, dialogue and division of tasks between various national networks, including the National CoARA Chapter, the steering group and working group for responsible assessment of researchers, National Open Science and Research Coordination working group on rewards and incentives, and Finn-ARMA groups on research assessment and publication metrics.
9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments	TSV is committed to communicating regularly on the progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the commitments on its public website and other communication channels by means of news pieces, briefs and reports.

CoARA Commitment	TSV Actions
<p>10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research</p>	<p>TSV is committed to contributing to evidence-based development of assessment practices and sharing the results and data. Examples of TSV contributions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Making FAIRer assessments possible. Final report of EOSC Co-Creation projects: "European overview of career merit systems" and "Vision for research data in research careers". Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4701375• Publication Forum 2010–2020: Self-evaluation report of the Finnish quality classification system of peer-reviewed publication channels. https://doi.org/10.23847/isbn.9789525995442• GraspOS Deliverable D2.1 "OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report". Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098095• Researchers' views on diversity of career assessment criteria in Finland: a survey report. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11612535